

Modelling the Thermomechanical Response of Metastable Beta-Titanium Shape Memory Alloys

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INTRODUCTION

Over the last two decades, new nickel-free shape memory alloys (SMAs) based on metastable titanium alloys have been discovered. To exploit their potential in biomedical or other applications, a reliable and effective computational tool is needed. Although constitutive models of various SMA families (e.g. Cu-based or Fe-based) can be found in the literature, those for NiTi and NiTi-based SMA remain by far the most elaborated ones. Indeed, the strongly coupled influence of stress and temperature on the martensitic transformation, the easy reorientation and mechanical stabilization, tension-compression asymmetry – these and many other phenomena were successfully captured. However, the transferability to the metastable titanium alloys remains to be explored. The present work reports the first attempts in this direction and introduces a finite-strain model for a stabilized superelastic metastable beta-Ti alloy with the nominal composition Ti–18Zr–11Nb–3Sn (at.%), hereinafter denoted as TiZrNbSn.

METHODS

A small-strain constitutive model for the reversible mechanical behaviour of NiTi SMA, originally developed in [1], was modified to capture the stable response of the TiZrNbSn alloy. The free energy function was refined to reflect the particular morphology of hysteresis loops. Experimental data were used to fit the superelastic response at room temperature. Due to the lack of data, no tension-compression asymmetry was considered. Finally, the logarithmic strain space approach, originally devised by Miehe and co-workers in [2], was employed to reliably simulate evolutionary problems, including large rotations and/or finite strains [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As a validation problem, the bending of a slender cantilever beam with a square cross-section and a height-to-length ratio equal to 30 was simulated. The deflection of the free end was prescribed from an initially horizontal position, with no volume forces considered. The results of the model fitted to the TiZrNbSn alloy are shown and compared with those of the model fitted to NiTi in Fig. 1. It shows the distribution of the martensite volume fraction at the final

Fig. 1: Computational simulation of the bending of a cantilever beam made from NiTi or TiZrNbSn SMA. The initial shape with the FE mesh superimposed (top left). The deformed configuration with the distribution of volume fraction of martensite (VFM) superimposed (left), and the corresponding evolution of force with deflection of the free end of the cantilever (right).

deflection (left) and the force-deflection loading curve (right). Mainly due to more than three times lower maximum attainable transformation strain and no tension-compression asymmetry, the results of TiZrNbSn differ significantly from those for NiTi; see more details and a discussion in [3]. Such differences must be carefully considered in application design.

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